

**ACTUAL ISSUES OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY
RIGHT PROTECTION (Copyright AND ARTIFICIAL
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direction****ORCID:009-0005-6810-02-05****yusupbayevaeleonora@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20233284>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 12th May 2026Accepted: 14th May 2026Online: 16th May 2026**KEYWORDS***Artificial intelligence, copyright,
intellectual property, originality,
creative work, human-centered
approach, Supreme Court
statistics, Constitution***ABSTRACT***This thesis analyzes the legal status of products created by artificial intelligence (AI) as objects of copyright. The author examines the evolution of the concept of "creativity," international judicial practice, and the newly revised Constitution and legislative framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The text also substantiates the need to consider AI products to be in the public domain due to their lack of a "human creative spark" and the latest judicial statistics in Uzbekistan.*

Today we live in a time when the creative labor and intellectual property of man, formed over many years, have faced an unexpected opponent. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are writing texts, drawing pictures, and creating music in seconds that we work on mentally. Most importantly, this technology did not emerge on its own – it is enriching itself with data based on the works created by us, humans. At the same time, the question arises: is the product created by AI a real work of art or just a set of algorithms? If AI creates something new using human creativity, who is its true author? And to what extent is copyright respected in this country? In the main part of the thesis, we analyze the aforementioned questions.

To find a legal solution to the problems raised above, it is first necessary to analyze the content and significance of the concept of "creativity" in the copyright system.

Legal evolution of the concept of "creativity," the basis of intellectual property rights are the principles of "Originality" and "Modicum of creativity." In the case of *Feist Publications, Inc. v. Rural Telephone Service Co.* (1991), only the "creative spark of humanity" is protected. AI relies on statistical patterns (Big Data) rather than emotions. Therefore, the AI product is evaluated not as "intellectual labor," but as a "result of a technical process."

Viewing AI as the result of a technical process, in turn, further strengthens the human-centered approach (Anthropocentrism) in current legislation. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Copyright and Related Rights," an author is a natural person who has created a work through their creative labor. AI cannot be the subject of non-property rights (name, immunity) and social contract. In international practice, specifically according to USCO's position, AI products with minimal human input are considered "Public Domain" (public domain). A vivid example of this is the work of the comic strip "Zarya of the Dawn"[1].

Also, the right is not only a privilege, but also a responsibility; Since AI cannot bear legal responsibility, granting it authorship status creates a loophole in the legal procedure.

Copyright Protection in Uzbekistan. National legislation clearly defines the scope of the author's property and personal non-property rights. According to Article 1056 of the Civil Code, the author has the exclusive right to use the work in any way. Today, copyright has become a major sector of the economy. For example, in 2019, the share of this sector in the US was 11.99% of GDP (\$2.5 trillion). At the international level, organizations such as CISAC play an important role in collecting royalties. The provision on the amount of compensation (from 20 to 1000 times the base calculated value), included in Article 65 of the legislation of Uzbekistan, serves as an important basis for determining a specific measure of liability for offenses in judicial practice [2].

Against the backdrop of these global trends, it is important to analyze Uzbekistan's national legislation and strategic reforms in the field of intellectual property protection. According to Article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, "Everyone has the right to the protection of their spiritual and material interests arising from scientific, literary, or artistic works of which they are the author." Accordingly, ensuring the interests of authors and their legal successors has risen to the level of state policy worldwide. After all, the introduction of effective mechanisms for the protection of intellectual property forms the foundation of the economy of developed countries. Worldwide, the administrative management of international intellectual property treaties is carried out by the UN's specialized organization, the World Intellectual Property Organization. Uzbekistan has been an equal member of this organization since December 25, 1991. The organization was founded on April 26, 1970. A number of regulatory legal acts aimed at protecting intellectual property have been adopted in our country, and today the Civil Code, the laws "On Intellectual Property," "On Patents," "On Copyright and Related Rights," and other regulatory documents regulate the sphere. In particular, in the new edition of the Constitution adopted in 2023, such norms as the legal protection of intellectual property, freedom of scientific and artistic creativity, and the inviolability of private property have taken a special place. This placed the field of intellectual property in a special place within the system of constitutional rights. In particular, the Constitution guarantees everyone freedom of scientific, technical, and artistic creativity, the right to use cultural achievements, and the protection of intellectual property by law. The statistics of cases considered in the courts show that the number of disputes in the field is increasing every year. The implementation of legal norms in life is carried out directly by the court is reflected in practice. For example, according to data from the Supreme Court, while 94 cases of this nature were heard in economic courts in 2023, their number decreased sharply to 25 in 2024. However, the fact that 78 cases were heard in the first six months of 2025 indicates that the number of disputes is growing sharply again. This situation indicates an increasing number of economic disputes related to intellectual property and the growing need to resolve them [3].

In conclusion, although artificial intelligence develops based on human creativity, it cannot be an independent subject of authorship due to its lack of "human creative spark" and legal liability. The experience of Uzbekistan and judicial statistics show that the protection of intellectual property is the key to economic stability. In the future, the only way to ensure

legal justice is to regulate AI products as a sui generis (special type) object and shift the responsibility not to the algorithm, but to the person who used it..

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